

Synthesis of some aryl/heteroaryl tetrazole derivatives and their mass fragmentation study[†]

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Manuscript received 20 August 1999

Synthesis of some aryl and heteroaryl tetrazole derivatives are described and their electron impact mass fragmentation pattern is discussed.

The discovery of the pharmacological and biochemical properties of tetrazole derivatives has resulted in enormous development over the past few years. Tetrazole derivatives are reported¹ to exhibit a variety of biological activities such as antiallergic, antihypertensive, antipyretic, analgesic, anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties. 5-Substituted tetrazoles are metabolically stable compounds having comparable acidity as that of the corresponding carboxylic acids. Change of biological activity of various carboxylic acids on replacement of carboxylic acid function by 5-tetrazolyl group is also reported². 1,5-Disubstituted 1*H*-tetrazoles have long been known for their pharmaceutical activity³ as stimulants or depressants on the central nervous system and are reported to show oral antidiabetic⁴, antithrombotic⁵ and antimicrobial properties. In view of the above observations we undertook to synthesise some 1,5-disubstituted aryl and heteroaryl tetrazole derivatives.

Several methods for the synthesis of 1,5-disubstituted tetrazoles have been reported³. The conventional synthesis of this type of compounds involves the thermal addition of organic azides to electron deficient nitriles, thermolysis, photolysis, cyclization of *in situ* generated imidoylazides, azidolysis of azalactones, cyclodehydration of acetyl tetrazoles, alkylation of 5-substituted tetrazoles, action of hydrazoic acid on nitriles or carbodimides and reaction of acetylhydrazines with diazonium compounds. The cyclization of imidoylazides is a major route for preparation of 1,5-disubstituted tetrazoles. The *N*-substituted amides (**1a-f**) were prepared by treatment of the appropriate primary amine with 2,4-dichlorobenzoyl chloride (Scheme 1). A few *N*-(heteroaryl)substituted amides (**1g** and **1h**) were also prepared as these compounds have been reported⁶ to exhibit biological activities like antifungal and antibacterial. The synthetic sequences leading to the formation of these compounds taking amino heteroaryl as the starting material are outlined in Scheme 1.

The open-chain imidoyl chlorides (**2a-f**) required for the

preparation of tetrazole derivatives were obtained⁷ by heating a mixture of appropriate anilide with PCl_5 . The imidoyl chloride residue was then dissolved in DMF with minimum exposure to air and used immediately in tetrazole synthesis.

Scheme 1

Most imide chlorides, $\text{R}'\text{C}(\text{Cl})=\text{NR}$, excepting those derived from *N*-arylaromatic amides in which both R and R' are aryl groups, are rather unstable substances which undergo thermal decomposition quite readily. The restriction to imide chlorides derived from anilides appeared⁸ to be based on earlier work by Von Braun *et al.* in which it was shown that the chlorides of aliphatic amides of the type $\text{RCH}_2\text{C}(\text{Cl})=\text{NR}^1$ (where R is either hydrogen or an aliphatic group and R¹ either aliphatic or aromatic) were characterized by such great reactivity that they could not be isolated. The *N*-(heteroaryl)substituted imidoyl chlorides (**2g** and **2h**) were prepared following the same method mentioned above.

The cyclization of imidoyl azides is a major route for preparation of 1,5-disubstituted tetrazoles. It has been reported⁹ that for this synthesis two structural features are required: (i) the imino lone-pair and the azido group need to be in the *cis*-arrangement and (ii) a sufficient electron density is required on the imino system to allow for the for-

[†] Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th birthday.

mation of the aromatic tetrazole ring. The probable mechanism has been discussed in Scheme 2. If either or both the substituent R^1 and R^2 on imidoyl chloride (2) are strongly electron-withdrawing, the electron-donating azido group may remain as such and fails to cyclize. Synthesis of tetrazoles by this route is a matter of generating imidoyl chloride which usually cyclizes spontaneously. The azide addition to the imidoyl chloride may be conceived to proceed in a two-step reaction via an azidoazomethene (2) intermediate or in a single-step concerted cycloaddition leading to the formation of the tetrazole ring.

Scheme 2

In a typical reaction, a mixture of NaN_3 and DMF was treated with a solution of imidoyl chloride in DMF. The mixture was treated with water to yield 1,5-disubstituted tetrazole (*vide* Experimental). Compounds **1a-f** were prepared by this method. For compounds **1g** and **1h**, the temperature of reaction mixture was maintained in ice-cooled condition ($0-5^\circ$) during addition of imidoyl chloride to get good yield. In the IR spectra, the tetrazoles showed no absorption at $1600-2400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ where azides showed absorption (near 2100 cm^{-1}). Both tetrazole and azides showed a band at $1095-1105\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and one or two other bands in the $1100-1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. These IR data have been reported¹⁰ to be characteristic of the tetrazole ring. The $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra of compounds **3a-h** showed aromatic protons resonance in the range $\delta 7.0-8.5$. The chemical shifts of the aromatic protons depend on the nature of the substituent group in the aromatic ring.

Mass spectral data of 1,5-disubstituted tetrazole derivatives : The electron impact studies on 1,5-disubstituted tetrazoles appeared in the literature¹¹⁻¹³. The skeletal rearrangement and fragmentation patterns have been studied for tetrazole derivatives (**3a-h**) under electron impact. The probable fragmentation and rearrangement in the molecule of 1-phenyl-5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)tetrazole are presented in Scheme 3. It has been observed from the mass spectra of the tetrazole derivatives that the most probable pattern of fragmentation may be discussed in the following themes : (i) absence of parent molecular ion, (ii) M-28 fragment and (iii) formation of carbodiimide.

Absence of parent molecular ion peak : The parent molecular ion for the 1,5-disubstituted tetrazoles is found

to be absent in all the compounds. It has been reported¹⁴ that the parent molecular ion was not present in their mass spectrum. This observation indicates that these compounds are not stable in the electron impact.

Scheme 3

(M^+-28) fragment : It has been observed from the mass spectra of 1,5-disubstituted tetrazoles that there was no molecular ion M^+ , instead an intense M^+-28 peak appeared^{15,16}, which was sometime base peak. The fragmentation may be represented as the loss of one nitrogen molecule from tetrazole nucleus of the molecule. This M^+-28 peak appeared as a cluster of isotopic peaks characteristics for dichloro compounds. The most prominent cleavages of N_2-N_3 bond are being observed in all the compounds resulting the M^+-28 ion. It seems clear that the fragmentation pattern observed for 1,5-disubstituted tetrazoles may vary considerably with the nature of the tetrazole ring substituents. The fragmentation are sensitive to substituents on the 1-phenyl ring and the pattern for a variety of substituted phenyl derivatives have been reported¹⁷.

Formation of carbodiimides : 1,5-Disubstituted tetrazoles when heated strongly breaks up to give carbodiimides (**I**) accompanying in some cases by significant amount of 2-arylarimidazole (**II**) (Scheme 4)^{15,18}. Since the two reactions occurring embody competition between one involving migration of a group from carbon to nitrogen and the one involving cyclization to a benzene ring without migration, it is of interest to examine the effect of substituents on the group that might migrate. A *para*-chloro substituent retards the migration of phenyl from C to N in the

Beckmann rearrangement resulting significantly higher yield of arylimidazole (II). Conversely, a *para*-methyl substituent accelerates the migration of an aryl group in the Beckmann rearrangement and promotes carbodiimide (I) formation.

Scheme 4

Simple fragmentation : The (M^+-28) fragment 'A' undergoes further fragmentation (Scheme 3) producing simple fragments. The most prominent cleavages of N–C and N–N bonds are being observed in all the compounds resulting the ion $[C_6H_3Cl_2-CN]^+$ at m/z 171/173 (100%). This ion loses $-C=N$ to give $[C_6H_3Cl_2]^+$ at m/z 145/147 (28%). The loss of this ion from the fragment 'A' gives rise to m/z 90/91 (50%) the ion $[C_6H_5N]^+$ in compound 3a. For other compounds, the mass of this ion depends on the substituents present on the phenyl ring. The elimination of $[C_6H_3Cl_2CN]^+$ ion is supported by metastable ions which is characteristic for heterocyclic compounds. The fragment at m/z 75/77 (65%) for $[C_6H_3]^+$ fragment observed for all the compounds is formed by loss of Cl, then HCN followed by again a chlorine radical (Scheme 3).

Experimental

The m.ps. were taken in a Buchi oil-heated apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237B spectrophotometer, 1H NMR spectra ($CDCl_3/DMSO-d_6$) on a EM 360 L (60 MHz) spectrometer and the mass spectra on a Finigan-Mat (INCOS-50) spectrometer.

2,4-Dichlorophenylarylanilides (1a-h) : To a solution of aniline (0.93 g 0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was added dropwise a solution of 2,4-dichlorobenzoyl chloride (2.08 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (5 ml) with continuous stirring. External cooling was applied when needed. The reactants were refluxed on a water-bath for 1 h. The excess of ethanol was distilled off and the solid obtained was treated with water (30 ml) followed by washing with aq. $NaHCO_3$ (50%) and then crystallized from ethanol, (1a; 2.38 g, 90%), m.p.

130°. Other compounds (1b-h) were prepared by the same procedure.

Substituted imidoyl chlorides (2a-h) : A mixture of an amide (1a; 2.65 g, 0.01 mol) and PCl_5 (2.08 g, 0.01 mol) was taken in a round bottom flask connected to a water aspirator through a drying tube to remove HCl and $POCl_3$ formed during the reaction. The mixture was heated until the evolution of HCl gas ceased (0.5–1 h). To prepare compounds 2g-h the mixture of appropriate amide and PCl_5 was heated for 1 h at 100°. The imidoyl chloride residue was then cooled and dissolved in DMF (50–75 ml) with minimum exposure to air and used immediately for tetrazole synthesis.

1,5-Disubstituted tetrazoles (3a-h) : A mixture of NaN_3 (1.3 g, 0.02 mol) and DMF (25–30 ml) was taken in a two-necked flask attached with drying tube and a funnel, and immersed in a water-bath maintained at 20–25° (0–5° for compounds 3g-h) throughout the course of the reaction. To it a solution of the imidoyl chloride (0.01 mol) in DMF was added dropwise with stirring over a period of 45–60 min. After the addition was complete, the stirring was continued for an additional 30 min. The mixture was then treated with water, just enough to produce a cloudiness, and cooled, when the 1,5-disubstituted tetrazole separated out as shining crystals. Similar treatment of the filtrate yielded an additional amount of tetrazole. The products were filtered, washed with ethanol-water (1 : 1) mixture and pressed dry. The crystalline material was then washed with water to remove inorganic matter such as NaCl and NaN_3 . The tetrazoles thus obtained were crystallized from ethanol-water (1 : 1) mixture : 3a (2.32 g, 80%), m.p. 165°; ν_{max} 1600, 1500, 1095, 1125 cm^{-1} , δ 7.25–7.80 (m, ArH); m/z 262 (M^+-28 , 30%), 173/171 (100%), 147/145 (28%), 90/91 (50%), 77/75 (65%); 3b (85%), 165°; ν_{max} 1600, 1500, 1450 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.25–7.50 (m, ArH), m/z 341 (M^+-28 , 100%), 173/171 (85%), 147/145 (30%), 90/91 (20%); 3c (95%), 120°; ν_{max} 1610, 1590, 1445, 1380, 1090 cm^{-1} , δ 7.50–7.62 (m, ArH), 7.25–7.40 (m, 3 × ArH), m/z 307 (M^+-28 , 100%), 261 (55%), 173/171 (85%), 147/145 (15%), 90 (100%); 3d (90%), 110°; ν_{max} 1600, 1505, 1450, 1350 cm^{-1} , δ 6.52–7.36 (m, ArH), m/z 296 (M^+-28 , 100%), 173/171 (90%), 147/145 (18%), 91/90 (100%); 3e (75%), 149°; ν_{max} 1580, 1500, 1435 cm^{-1} , δ 6.50–7.32 (ArH), m/z (307, M^+-28 , 100%), 173/171 (80%), 147/145 (30%), 90 (60%); 3f (70%), 158°; ν_{max} 1650, 1500, 1450 cm^{-1} , δ 6.80–7.40 (m, ArH), m/z 296 (M^+-28 , 100%), 173/171 (80%), 147/145 (50%), 90 (100%); 3g (70%), 175°; δ 7.15–7.55 (m, ArH), m/z 345 (M^+-28 , 30%), 173/171 (80%), 147/145

(30%); **3h** (68%), m.p. 180°, δ 7.0–7.60 (m, ArH), m/z 414 (M^+ -28, 30%), 244 (60%), 173/171 (85%), 147/145 (38%), 91 (28%).

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge and thank Director, Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat, for the facilities. The authors are also thankful to Dr. J. C. S. Katakya, Scientist of this laboratory for his help in many ways while preparing the manuscript.

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